

MARKETING EFFICIENCY OF SEA FOOD PRODUCTION IN BAJO DISTRICT BOALEMO PROVINCE GORONTALO

Lis Melissa Yapanto

Management Aquatic Department
Universitas Negeri Gorontalo
email: lizrossler@ung.ac.id
Hp: 082123042121

Abstract

The study was conducted in Bajo Tilamuta Village, Boalemo District, Gorontalo Province. Marketing is one of the most important activities in marketing the existing seafood in Bajo Village in Boalemo, because one of the factors that become obstacle is the availability of adequate infrastructure. In Bajo Lemito Village, Boalemo Regency has potential for high value fishery such as; Sea Cucumbers and Pearls, Mabe, Japing. The purpose of this study is to study the state of the economy in the Village Bajo Tilamuta Boalemo district, living conditions of fishermen, production and marketing. The research method is descriptive by using purposive sampling method that is taking direct samples because it is known before that the sample can represent the population. While the data analysis using quantitative and qualitative methods. Qualitative method is to provide a discussion of quantitative data relating to theoretical aspects and separated by category to get conclusions.

The results of the study provide information that the sea cucumber is classified as having a good marketing efficiency and categorized into the already efficient marketing while marketing pearl shells, Mabe, Japing marketing has not been efficient.

Keywords: Marketing Efficiency, Sea Cucumber sea cucumbers, shellfish mabe, japing shells

Introduction

Marketing is one of the most important activities to help increase the income of fishermen. Marketing is one of the most important activities to improve the economy, especially in the field of fisheries. In marketing the seafood it is necessary to provide facilities and infrastructure such as fishing port, TPI, fish market and others. Bajo fishermen in Boalemo Regency produce seafood such as: Sea cucumbers, Mother shells, Mabe shells and Japing shells. Mubyarto (1985) states, pemsaran or distribution is a kind of economic activity that serves to bring or deliver goods from producers to consumers. Hippy (1992) that the types of sea products that exist in the village of Bajo Boalemo Regency are fish such as tude fish, skipjack, mullet, sea cucumber and shellfish. According Sugiono (2001),

marketing institutions according to the control of commodities traded can be distinguished on three: 1. institutions that do not have but control objects, such as agents, brokers, selling brokers.

Materials And Method

The method used is the sampling method or sampling, because it has been done pre-survey before, then the village that is sampled is Bajo Tilamuta village Boalemo Regency where most of the population is Bajo tribe. Sampling is done purposively, ie selecting the sample directly because it has been known before that the selected sample can represent it. While the data analysis using the trading margin as a measuring tool that is the average price of producers divided the market selling price. According Sutarno (2014), mathematically the amount of marketing margin can be calculated based on the formula $MP = Pr - Pf$. For efficiency can be seen from the percentage of income received by the manufacturer.

Result And Discussion

The average price / kg of these types of seafood can be seen in the table below:

No types of seafood		Harga Rata-rata /kg			
		Fishermen	Collectors traders	Wholesalers	Exporter
1	Teripang	140000	170000	190000	260000
2	Scallops Pearl	26000	29000	34000	63000
3	Mabe Shells	18000	22000	27000	47000
4	Japing Clams	14000	18000	24000	45000

From the table above can be seen that the margin obtained by wholesalers and exporters has a very large margin. While margi from fishermen to collecting merchants have a smaller difference than big traders. The highest marketing cost is in channel 3 which is a wholesaler.

Table 2. Average price of Bajo Fisherman Seaweed at producer level and consumer level

types of seafood	Price Rp / kg	
	Producer	Consumer
Sea cucumbers	140000	260000
Scallops Pearl	26000	34000
Mabe Shells	18000	29000
Japing Clams	14000	27000

Table 3.

Efficiency of marketing of marine products in Bajo Tilamuta village of Boalemo Distri

No	types of seafood	Percentage (%)		Efisiensi Pemasaran
		Fisherman	Exporter	Exporter
1	Sea cucumbers	53	47	efficient
2	Scallop Pearl	13	87	Not efficient
3	Mabe Shells	16	84	Not efficient
4	Japing Clams	19	81	Not efficient

Margin marketing is done to determine the marketing efficiency of a product from producer level to consumer level. Margin marketing is the price difference that occurs with the amount of profit in each marketing agency involved in marketing activities. There are several different cost components of each marketing channel pattern, thus impacting marketing margins on existing marketing institutions in Bajo Tilamuta village, Boalemo District, can be seen in Table 3 above.

Acknowledgment

Acknowledgments to the local government of Boalemo Regency which has helped a lot in this research as well as my thanks to the Dean of the Faculty of Fisheries and fellow lecturers at FPIK UNG.

References

- Yapanto,LM, Musa,Farid Th (2018) Distribution of Seafood Production in Bajo Sector of Gorontalo Province Indonesia. In: Distribution of Seafood Production in Bajo Sector of Gorontalo Province Indonesia. Zenodo, pp 2456–2165
- Sutarno, 2014. Kedelei Marketing Efficiency Analysis in Wonogiri District. E-Journal Agrineca.14.
- Kotler Philip, 1997. Fundamentals of Marketing, edition of the press, volume1 Erlangga.
- William Stanton J, 1997. Principles of Marketing, volume I, Erland, Jakarta. Meyer, Warren G et al, translated by Tien Sribimawati, 1988, Retail Marketing. Elex Media Komputindo,Jakarta.
- Anderson LG. 1986. Economic OF Fisheries Management. JohnWiley and Sons, NewYork.
- Marine Fishery Research Institute. 1992. Indonesia's Important Marine Fish. Jakarta. Center for Research and Development of Fisheries. Agricultural Research and Development Agency. Department of Agriculture of the Republic of Indonesia. Jakarta 170 p.

Fauzi A. 2010. Fishery Economy. PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama: Jakarta.

Suharto, B, Yapanto, L M (2019) Participation of the Community in Management of Tourist in the Village of Torosiaje Sub District Popayato District of Pohuwato Gorontalo Province. Participation of the Community in Management of Tourist in the Village of Torosiaje Sub District Popayato District of Pohuwato Gorontalo Province 3:8. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.2559497